

Stereocontrolled Synthesis of β -Lactams from Amidomalonates : Intermediates for Thienamycin, Carpetimycin and Analogs¹

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Complete stereocontrol of β -lactam formation can be achieved by the intra-molecular cyclisation of the epoxide of an *N*-acrylaminomalonate. The β -lactam so obtained is fused with a lactone ring derived from one of the ester groups of the malonate and the carbinol side chain generated by the stereospecific opening of the epoxide ring. Selective hydrolysis of the lactone group leads to a *trans* β -lactam; selective decarboxylation produces a *cis* β -lactam. The configuration of the carbinol side chain can be altered by a Mitsunobu reaction. The use of a *p* anisidinomalonate as the starting material permits easy formation of the *N*-unsubstituted β -lactams which are convenient intermediates for the synthesis of various carbapenem antibiotics, their epimers and analogs.

AN efficient synthesis of β -lactams described by Sheehan and Bose² in 1950 consists in the cyclisation of an α -haloacetamidomalonate (1) via intra-molecular alkylation in presence of triethylamine. A single β -lactam (2) is obtained in this reaction since the formation of *cis* and *trans* isomers is precluded by the symmetry of substitution at C-4. The ring formation involves S_N2 substitution at the halogen bearing carbon which then becomes C-3 of the four-membered ring³.

Further studies⁴ in our laboratory have demonstrated that competitive intra-molecular alkylation in the case of the dibromo compound (3) leads to selective cyclisation to a γ -lactam (4) in preference to a β -lactam (5). On the other hand, during the cyclisation of 6, a β -lactam (7) is formed rather than a δ -lactam (8) (Scheme 1). We⁵ also showed that cyclisation of an *N*-acrylaminomalonate, such

Scheme 1

as 9, led to a β -lactam (10) by internal Michael addition; no γ -lactam was formed.

In recent years, a number of β -lactam antibiotics (*viz.* thienamycin, carpetimycin and olivanic acid) have been discovered in nature that are characterised by a carbinol side chain in place of the usual amido side chain⁶. It occurred to us that β -lactams with this type of side chain could perhaps be generated by an internal displacement reaction involving the epoxide ring and the strategically placed carbanion in an intermediate, such as 13. However, the possibility of a γ -lactam formation could not be ruled out in the light of our earlier studies⁴ on the course of cyclisation of 3.

As a test case, the acrylamide (11) was prepared from benzyl phenylglycinate and oxidised to the epoxide 12 by reaction with *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid. Treatment of 12 with a strong base (for example, lithium di-isopropylamide) led to a single product 14. Spectral data showed that 14 is a β -lactam and not a γ -lactam (15) (Scheme 2).

From its ¹H nmr spectrum, the epoxide 12 appeared to be a single compound although two diastereomeric epoxides could be expected. Conversion of 12 to 14, therefore, could have produced two diastereomeric β -lactams in the racemic form

although the formation of only one isomer was observed.

Scheme 2

To preclude the possibility of the formation of diastereomeric products, the acrylamidomaltonate 16c was selected; this compound has no asymmetric centers and therefore a single racemic epoxide, 17c, and a single β -lactam (or γ -lactam) only could be formed.

Treatment of 17c with triethylamine led to a major product 18c that proved to be a lactone on the basis of ir and nmr spectral data. Obviously, during β -lactam formation through epoxide opening, the nascent hydroxyl group had reacted with an ester group to generate a lactone function. Since a *trans*-fused β -lactam is not possible in this case, the *cis*-fused β -lactam structure had to be assigned to 18c (Scheme 3). The nmr spectral data were fully consistent with this fused β -lactam structure.

- | | |
|--|-----------------|
| Ar | R |
| (a) C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ (p) | H |
| (b) C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃ (p) | H |
| (c) C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ (p) | CH ₃ |
| (d) C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃ (p) | CH ₃ |

Scheme 3

The above observation indicated the possibility of complete stereocontrol during the formation of a series of functionalised β -lactams. We^v had established through earlier studies that saponification of 1-(*p*-anisyl)-3-phenoxy-4,4-dicarboethoxycarbonyl-2-azetidinone led to the preferential hydrolysis of the less hindered *trans* ester group (Scheme 4). Decarboxylation under mild conditions then produced a *cis* β -lactam. Similar selected hydrolysis appeared reasonable for the ester or lactone carboxyl groups in 18 and analogs.

Scheme 4

The preparation of variously substituted *cis* and *trans* β -lactams from acrylamidomaltonates is described in the following sections. Some of these compounds are suitable as intermediates for the synthesis of naturally occurring β -lactam antibiotics.

While further development of this synthetic approach was in progress in our laboratory⁸, Shiozaki *et al.*^{9a} reported that the cyclisation of 19 produced a β -lactam 21, apparently *via* the initial formation of an epoxide 20 (Scheme 5). More recently an optically active glycidic acid amide has been used by Shiozaki *et al.*^{9b} and by Hanessian *et al.*¹⁰ to prepare optically active β -lactams as precursors for thienamycin.

Scheme 5

***cis*- β -Lactam :** A series of fused β -lactams (18) were prepared from amidomaltonates *via* the epoxide route. Decarboethoxylation of 18c under the influence of sodium chloride and aqueous dimethylsulphoxide¹¹ led to the formation of a *cis*-fused β -lactam 22c.

A number of methods are known for preparing *N*-unsubstituted β -lactams by the removal of an appropriate substituent placed on the β -lactam nitrogen. We selected the *p*-anisyl group as the *N*-substituent because it can be removed fairly easily by oxidation with cerium(IV) ammonium nitrate (CAN)¹². The β -lactam 22d obtained from easily prepared diethyl *p*-anisidinomaltonate was converted *via* CAN oxidation to the *N*-unsubstituted product 27.

***trans*- β -Lactam :** Using the same steps as for preparing 18c, the fused β -lactam 18a, 18b, and 18d were obtained in about 65% yield. The decarboethoxylation of 18d produced the fused β -lactam 22d as a minor product. The major product was a monocyclic β -lactam (28) which could be assigned *trans* stereochemistry on the basis of ¹H nmr spectral data¹(*J*_{3,4} 2.5 Hz). Obviously, the lactone

ring had been hydrolysed in preference to the ester group and the product had undergone decarboxylation. Chromatographic separation of these two types of products is easy because of the large difference in their polarity (Scheme 6).

Intermediates for β -lactam antibiotics: With the intention of preparing analogs of thienamycin, carpetimycin, olivanic acid, and related antibiotics, it was decided to devise a strategy that would require as intermediates *N*-unsubstituted, monocyclic β -lactams with appropriate functional groups at C-3 and C-4.

Scheme 6

Various pathways have been described in the literature^{6,13} for forming the five-membered ring systems in non-classical β -lactam antibiotics. An examination of these pathways shows that β -lactams of type 36a and 36b are convenient intermediates for the elaboration of the second ring.

Carpetimycin precursor: Carpetimycin with an achiral carbinol side chain is a simpler target than thienamycin and olivanic acid. Our starting material for carpetimycin is the achiral acrylamidomalonate 16d, the conversion of which to the racemic lactone 22d has been described in an earlier section. Lithium borohydride reduction of 22d produced the diol 24 which could be selectively acylated to produce the monocarbonate 25. The desired *N*-unsubstituted β -lactam 26 was obtained in good yield by the CAN oxidation of 25. This *cis* β -lactam is an appropriate intermediate for the construction of a five-membered ring to lead to a variety of analogs of carpetimycin.

Thienamycin precursor: Our starting material for thienamycin is the achiral amidomalonate 16b derived from easily available *trans*-crotonic acid. The configuration of the hydroxyl group which becomes part of the lactone ring in 18b follows from the known steric course of epoxide opening. Thus, the three centers of asymmetry in 18b are created in a single operation under complete stereocontrol.

The coupling constant of 7 Hz for coupling between H_a and H_b in 18b is indicative of the relative stereochemistry of these two protons; as is to be expected, our value is different from the 1.5 Hz value obtained for the corresponding protons in 29 observed by Shiozaki *et al.*⁹ who used a *cis* epoxide in contrast to our *trans* epoxide.

Treatment of this lactone with sodium chloride and aqueous *N,N*-dimethyl formamide under reflux led to selective hydrolysis of the lactone ring and subsequent decarboxylation to provide in 70% yield a *trans* β -lactam 30. The configuration of the carbinol side chain in 30 corresponds to 8-epithienamycin.

The configuration of the carbinol side chain was easily changed by using the stereospecific Mitsunobu reaction¹⁴. Thus, the interaction of 30 with *p*-nitrobenzoic acid, triphenylphosphine and diethyl azodicarboxylate provided 37 with the correct relative configuration for a thienamycin derivative. On the other hand, acylation of 30 with *p*-nitrobenzoyl chloride in presence of triethylamine led to the 8-*epi* stereochemistry (Scheme 7).

Scheme 7

The functional groups in the fused β -lactams (18b) can be manipulated in a stereospecific fashion (Scheme 8). Some of the compounds so obtained, e.g. 34 and 35, are suitable as intermediates for the preparation of thienamycin and epimers. They have the substituents at the β -lactam nitrogen and at C-4 which would permit the construction of various five-membered rings by known methods^{6,13}.

Scheme 8

Olivanic acid is a *cis* β -lactam whereas thienamycin is a *trans* β -lactam but the relative configuration of C-6 and C-8 is the same for both compounds. Therefore, it should be possible to combine our techniques for carpetimycin and thienamycin derivatives and convert 18b to an appropriate intermediate for olivanic acid analogs and epimers.

Conclusions: The intra-molecular cyclisation of an *N*-acrylamidomalonate *via* its epoxide followed by selective hydrolysis of the lactone

group for a *trans* β -lactam and selective decarboalkoxylation for a *cis* β -lactam provides complete stereocontrol of the ring as well as the carbinol sidechain. Stereospecific inversion of the sidechain carbinol can be conducted *via* a Mitsunobu reaction. Since optically active *cis* glycidic acid can be obtained from commercially available D- and L-threonine, it should be possible to extend the amidomalonate approach to the preparation of both enantiomeric forms of carba-penem antibiotics and their C-6 and C-8 epimers.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. ^1H nmr spectra were recorded on a Varian EM-390 and Bruker SY200 NMR spectrometers. Chemical shifts are reported in parts per million from tetramethylsilane as internal standard, with the downfield direction taken as positive. Mass spectra were taken with a Hitachi RMU-7 spectrometer and a CIMS-Biospect instrument. The infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer infracord. Microanalyses were performed by Schwarzkopf Microanalytic Laboratory, Woodside, New York.

Diethyl N-aryl aminomalonates: These compounds prepared by the method of Sheehan and Bose², were obtained as oily liquids and used as such for subsequent steps.

Diethyl N-p-anisyl-, N-crotonoyl aminomalonate (16b): To a mixture of amine (10; 14.05 g, 0.05 mol), dichloromethane (150 ml) and pyridine (5 ml), a solution of crotonyl chloride (7.84 g, 7.20 ml, 0.075 mol) in dichloromethane (50 ml) was added slowly with stirring at 20° over a period of 30 min and the reaction mixture was further stirred for 2 h (monitored by tlc) at room temperature. The reaction mixture was washed with 1N HCl, water and brine. It was dried over MgSO_4 , and filtered. The filtrate on concentration gave an oil (16.80 g), which on purification by column chromatography (silica gel, 100-200 mesh; petroleum ether-ethyl acetate (8:2) as eluent) gave pure product 16b (14.83 g, 85%) crystallised from petroleum ether, m.p. 54° (Found: C, 61.85; H, 6.70; N, 4.46. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{23}\text{NO}_6$: C, 61.88; H, 6.64; N, 4.01%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1750 and 1670 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 1.2 (6H, t, J 7 Hz), 1.79 (3H, d, J 6 Hz), 3.8 (3H, s), 4.14 (4H, q, J 7 Hz), 5.55 (1H, s), 5.71 (1H, d, J 15 Hz), 6.9 (2H, d, J 9 Hz) 7.0 (1H, d, J 15 Hz) and 7.4 (2H, d, J 9 Hz); CIMS (reagent gas: NH_3) 350 ($\text{M}+\text{H}$)⁺ and 367 ($\text{M}+\text{NH}_4$)⁺.

Using similar reaction conditions benzyl phenylglycinate and 3,3-dimethylacryloyl chloride gave the amide 11 as an oily liquid in (93%); ν_{max} (nujol) 3360, 2910, 2080, 1940, 1710, 1620 and 715 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 1.76 (3H, s), 2.11 (3H, s), 5.07 (2H, s), 5.57 (1H, s), 5.66 (1H, d, J 8.33 Hz), 6.71 (1H, d, J 8.33 Hz), 7.17 (5H, s) and 7.24 (5H, s); CIMS (reagent gas: NH_3) 341 ($\text{M}+\text{NH}_4$)⁺.

Diethyl N-p-tolyl-, N-crotonylaminomalonate (16a): It was obtained as an oily product (84%) by reacting diethyl *p*-toluidinomalonate and crotonyl chloride; ν_{max} (neat) 1730, 1640 and 812 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 1.18 (6H, t, J 7 Hz), 1.68 (3H, d, J 6.6 Hz), 2.36 (3H, s), 4.13 (4H, q, J 7 Hz), 5.46 (1H, s), 5.63 (1H, d, J 16.6 Hz), 6.86 (1H, m) and 7.23 (4H, m); CIMS (reagent gas: NH_3) 334 ($\text{M}+\text{H}$)⁺.

Diethyl N-p-tolyl-, N-(3,3-dimethylacryloyl)aminomalonate (16c): It was similarly prepared by refluxing diethyl *p*-toluidinomalonate and 3,3-dimethylacryloyl chloride in benzene. The title compound was obtained as a thick oily product (90%); ν_{max} (neat) 1740, 1650 and 790 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 1.2 (6H, t, J 7 Hz), 1.81 (3H, s), 2.0 (3H, s), 2.34 (3H, s), 4.19 (4H, q, J 7 Hz), 5.47 (1H, s), 5.81 (1H, s) and 7.23 (4H, m); CIMS (reagent gas: NH_3) 365 ($\text{M}+\text{NH}_4$)⁺ and 348 ($\text{M}+\text{H}$)⁺.

Diethyl N-p-anisyl-, N-(3,3-dimethylacryloyl)aminomalonate (16d): It was obtained as a pale yellow solid (95%) by refluxing 3,3-dimethylacryloyl chloride and diethyl *p*-methoxyanilinomalonate in benzene, m.p. 76-78° (petroleum ether-ethyl acetate) (Found: C, 62.46; H, 6.94; N, 3.94. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{23}\text{NO}_6$: C, 62.80; H, 6.93; N, 3.85%); ν_{max} (nujol) 1745, 1715 and 1645 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 1.24 (3H, t, J 6 Hz), 3.67 (3H, s), 4.19 (2H, t, J 6 Hz), 4.5 (1H, s), 6.54 (2H, d, J 8 Hz) and 6.70 (2H, d, J Hz); CIMS (reagent gas: NH_3) 282 ($\text{M}+\text{H}$)⁺.

General method for epoxide formation: Epoxide 17b: To a solution of amide (16b; 6.98 g, 0.02 mol) in chloroform (50 ml), a solution of *m*-chloroperoxybenzoic acid (5.1 g, 0.03 mol) in chloroform (100 ml) was added over a period of 20 min and the resulting mixture was refluxed for 5 h (monitored by tlc). The excess per acid was decomposed by the treatment of 10% Na_2SO_3 solution. The chloroform layer was washed with saturated NaHCO_3 (3 \times 50 ml), water and brine. It was dried over MgSO_4 and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated to give an oily product (7.15 g). Column chromatography (Florosil, 100-200 mesh; ethyl acetate-petroleum ether, 2:8) gave 17b as a solid, m.p. 115-6° (Found: C, 59.20; H, 6.31; N, 3.57. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{23}\text{NO}_7$: C, 59.17; H, 6.34; N, 3.83%); ν_{max} (nujol) 1740, 1720, 1505, and 840 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 1.2 (6H, m), 1.42 (3H, d, J 7 Hz), 3.75 (3H, s), 3.85 (1H, d, J 4 Hz), 4.26 (5H, m), 4.8 (1H, s), 6.8 (2H, d, J 9 Hz) and 7.45 (2H, d, J 9 Hz); CIMS (reagent gas: NH_3) 366 ($\text{M}+\text{H}$)⁺ and 383 ($\text{M}+\text{NH}_4$)⁺.

Using the same reaction conditions the epoxides 12, 17a, 17c and 17d were prepared as viscous oils in 70-80% yields, and were used as such without further purification. The spectral data on these compounds is given below: 12: ν_{max} (nujol) 3400, 2960, 1740, 1670, 1500 and 700 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 1.14 (3H, s), 1.36 (3H, s), 3.28 (1H, s), 5.11 (2H, s),

5.59 (1H, d, J 8.3 Hz), 6.81 (1H, d, J 8.3 Hz), 7.18 (5H, s) and 7.31 (5H, s); CIMS (reagent gas: CH_4) 356 ($\text{M}+\text{NH}_4$)⁺. **17a**: ν_{max} (nujol) 1 730 and 1 652 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 1.29 (9H, m), 2.32 (3H, s), 3.41 (1H, d, J 16 Hz), 4.25 (5H, m), 5.46 (1H, s) and 7.3 (4H, m); CIMS (reagent gas: NH_3) 367 ($\text{M}+\text{NH}_4$)⁺ and 350 ($\text{M}+\text{H}$)⁺. **17c**: ν_{max} (nujol) 1 735 and 1 660 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 1.41 (12H, m), 2.33 (3H, s), 3.32 (1H, s), 4.3 (4H, m), 5.43 (1H, s) and 7.24 (4H, m); CIMS (reagent gas: NH_3) 381 ($\text{M}+\text{NH}_4$)⁺ and 364 ($\text{M}+\text{H}$)⁺. **17d**: ν_{max} (neat) 1 730 and 1 670 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 1.04 (3H, s), 1.22 (6H, t, J 7 Hz), 1.32 (3H, s), 3.05 (1H, s), 3.76 (3H, s), 4.1 (4H, m), 5.43 (1H, s), 6.9 (2H, d, J 9 Hz) and 7.36 (2H, d, J 9 Hz); CIMS (reagent gas: NH_3) 379 ($\text{M}+\text{H}$)⁺, 397 ($\text{M}+\text{NH}_4$)⁺.

Bicyclic β -lactam (18b)¹⁵: To a solution of epoxide (**17b**; 7.1 g) in chloroform (80 ml), a solution of triethylamine (4 ml) in chloroform (20 ml) was added and the reaction mixture was refluxed with stirring for 6 h (monitored by tlc). The cooled reaction mixture was washed successively with 1N HCl, water and brine, and dried (MgSO_4). The methylene chloride was removed under reduced pressure to give an oily crude product (5.58 g), which on purification by column chromatography (silica gel, 100-200 mesh; petroleum ether-ethyl acetate (7:3) as eluent) yielded pure **18b** (4.033 g, 65%) which was crystallised from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether, m.p. 93-94° (Found: C, 60.27; H, 5.76; N, 4.40. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_5$: C, 60.18; H, 5.37; N, 4.39%); ν_{max} (nujol) 1 750 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 1.28 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz), 1.63 (3H, d, J 8 Hz), 3.78 (3H, s), 4.11 (1H, d, J 8 Hz), 4.33 (2H, q, J 7.2 Hz), 4.92 (1H, m), 6.86 (2H, d, J 9 Hz) and 7.35 (2H, d, 9 Hz); CIMS (reagent gas: NH_3) 337 ($\text{M}+\text{H}$).

Bicyclic β -lactam (18a): It was prepared as described under **18b** by cyclising the epoxyamide **17a** with triethylamine, (54%), m.p. 94-5° (Found: C, 62.04; H, 5.58; N, 3.92. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_5$: C, 63.36; H, 5.65; N, 4.62%); ν_{max} (nujol) 1 760, 1 500 and 810 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 1.28 (3H, t, J 7 Hz), 1.62 (3H, d, J 6 Hz), 2.31 (3H, s), 4.12 (1H, d, J 6 Hz), 4.33 (2H, q, J 7 Hz), 4.91 (1H, m) and 7.3 (4H, m); CIMS (reagent gas: NH_3) 321 ($\text{M}+\text{NH}_4$)⁺ and 304 ($\text{M}+\text{H}$)⁺.

Bicyclic β -lactam (19c): It was obtained from **17c** (60%), m.p. 79-81° (Found: C, 64.54; H, 6.14; N, 4.261. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{18}\text{NO}_5$: C, 64.37; H, 6.03; N, 4.41%); ν_{max} (nujol) 1 765, 1 520 and 822 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 1.3 (3H, t, J 7 Hz), 1.58 (3H, s), 1.62 (3H, s), 2.3 (3H, s), 3.82 (1H, s), 4.35 (2H, q, J 7 Hz) and 7.28 (4H, m); CIMS (reagent gas: NH_3) 355 ($\text{M}+\text{NH}_4$)⁺ and 318 ($\text{M}+\text{H}$)⁺.

Bicyclic β -lactam (18d): It was formed (73%), m.p. 127-128°, by the cyclisation of **17d** using the conditions described above; ν_{max} (KBr) 1 745, 1 715, 1 645 and 1 625 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 1.24 (3H, t, J 6 Hz), 3.67 (2H, s), 4.19 (2H, t, J 6 Hz) and 4.5 (1H, s).

3-(2'-Hydroxyisopropyl)-4-phenyl-4-carbethoxy-carbonylazetidine-2-one (14): To a THF solution of **12** (5.19 g), LDA (3.4 g, 0.034 M) at -78° under nitrogen atmosphere was added dropwise and the reactants were stirred for 1 h. The reaction was quenched by pouring the reaction mixture in saturated NaCl solution. The reaction mixture was extracted with methylene chloride. The organic layer was dried (MgSO_4), filtered and evaporated under reduced pressure to yield a crude oil. This oily product was purified by column chromatography using silica-gel as the absorbant and benzene-ethyl acetate as the eluting solvent to afford the product (**14**; 1.5 g); ν_{max} (nujol) 3 300, 1 760, 1 500, 1 460 and 700 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 1.01 (3H, s), 1.23 (3H, s), 2.46 (1H, b), 4.61 (1H, s), 5.17 (2H, s) and 7.46 (1H, b); CIMS (reagent gas: NH_3) 357 ($\text{M}+\text{NH}_4$)⁺.

Decarboethoxylation of 18c: A mixture of the bicyclic β -lactam (**18c**; 3.17 g, 0.01 mol), sodium chloride (1.2 g, 0.02 mol), water (1 ml) and dimethylsulphoxide (20 ml) was refluxed under nitrogen atmosphere for 4 h. Dimethylsulphoxide was distilled off under reduced pressure and the residue was dissolved in methylene chloride (200 ml). The methylene chloride extract was washed with water (3×50 ml), brine (2×30 ml), dried (Na_2SO_4) and filtered. Filtrate on evaporation under reduced pressure gave a solid mass which on crystallisation from ethyl acetate-hexane gave **22c** (1.9 g, 79%), m.p. 156-158°; ν_{max} (nujol) 1 745, 1 500 and 800 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 1.48 (3H, s), 1.62 (3H, s), 2.32 (3H, s), 3.68 (1H, d, J 6 Hz), 4.6 (1H, d, J 6 Hz) and 7.24 (4H, m); CIMS (reagent gas: NH_3) 263 ($\text{M}+\text{NH}_4$)⁺.

Decarboethoxylation of 18d: A mixture of β -lactam **18d** (1.665 g, 0.005 mol), DMF (15 ml), sodium chloride (585 mg, 0.01 mol) and water (0.18 ml, 0.01 mol) was refluxed for 12 h under nitrogen atmosphere. The excess DMF was distilled off under reduced pressure. The residue was taken up in methylene chloride (60 ml). The methylene chloride solution was repeatedly washed with water (4×20 ml), brine (2×20 ml) and dried (Na_2SO_4). It was then filtered and the filtrate on concentration gave a mixture (1.25 g), which was separated by flash column chromatography (silica gel, 230-400 mesh, chloroform-ethyl acetate-petroleum ether, 10:0.5:0.5).

Less polar component (520 mg, 39.8%) was characterised as the bicyclic β -lactam (**22d**), m.p. 153-4° (Found: C, 63.67; H, 6.06; N, 5.20. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{18}\text{NO}_4$: C, 64.36; H, 5.79; N, 5.36%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1 770 and 1 735 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 1.58 (3H, s), 1.67 (3H, s), 3.70 (1H, d, J 5 Hz), 3.78 (3H, s), 4.67 (1H, d, J 5 Hz), 6.93 (2H, d, J 8 Hz) and 7.51 (2H, d, J 8 Hz); CIMS (reagent gas: NH_3) 279 ($\text{M}+\text{NH}_4$)⁺.

The more polar compound (450 mg, 29.3%) was characterised as the monocyclic β -lactam (**28**), m.p. 97-98° (Found: C, 62.42; H, 6.81; N, 4.88. Calcd.

for $C_{16}H_{21}NO_3$: C, 62.53; H, 6.89; N, 4.56%; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 450 and 1 730 cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 1.2 (3H, t, J 7 Hz), 1.3 (3H, s), 1.45 (3H, s), 3.27 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz), 3.72 (3H, s), 4.2 (2H, q, J Hz), 4.46 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz), 6.75 (2H, d, J 9 Hz) and 7.2 (2H, d, J 9 Hz); CIMS (reagent gas: NH_3) 308 (M+H)⁺.

cis-N-p-Toluidino-3-(2'-hydroxyisopropyl)-4-hydroxymethylazeti line-2-one (23): To a stirred solution of lithium borohydride (0.52 g, 0.025 mol) in diglyme (10 ml), was added dropwise a solution of 22c (4.29 g, 0.02 mol) in diglyme (50 ml) at 0° over a period of 1 h. The reaction mixture was then heated on a steam-bath for 3 h. After cooling, the reactants were poured over crushed ice containing dilute hydrochloric acid. The reaction mixture was then extracted with ethyl acetate (3 × 100 ml). The combined ethyl acetate extracts were washed with water (2 × 100 ml), brine (2 × 50 ml), dried ($MgSO_4$) and filtered. Evaporation of the solvent under reduced pressure gave 23 (3.89 g, 80%), m.p. 216-218° (ethyl acetate) (Found: C, 67.30; H, 7.66; N, 5.45. Calcd. for $C_{14}H_{19}NO_3$: C, 67.45; H, 7.68; N, 5.62%); ν_{\max} (nujol) 3 180, 1 760, 1 500 and 800 cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 1.35 (3H, s), 1.45 (3H, s), 2.28 (3H, s), 2.52 (1H, b), 3.32 (1H, d), 4.12 (1H, m), 4.25 (1H, d, J Hz), 7.24 (4H, m); CIMS (reagent gas: NH_3) 250 (M+H)⁺ and 267 (M+NH₄)⁺.

cis-N-(p-Methoxyphenyl)-3-(2'-hydroxyisopropyl)-4-hydroxymethylazetidone-2-one (24): Using the same reaction conditions as described under 23, the title compound was obtained (76%) from 22d, m.p. 212-213° (Found: C, 63.02; H, 7.17; N, 5.54. Calcd. for $C_{14}H_{19}NO_4$: C, 63.38; H, 7.22; N, 5.28%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 200, 1 730, 1 510 and 835 cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 1.35 (3H, s), 1.49 (3H, s), 3.42 (1H, d, J 5.7 Hz), 3.76 (3H, s), 4.00-4.30 (3H, m), 5.62 (2H, m), 6.86 (2H, d, J 8.7 Hz) and 7.38 (2H, d, J 8.7 Hz); CIMS (reagent gas: NH_3) 266 (M+H)⁺ and 283 (M+NH₄)⁺.

β-Lactam carbonate (25): To a suspension of the diol 24 (265 mg, 0.001 mol) in methylene chloride (25 ml), dimethyl aminopyridine (265 mg, 0.002 mol) was added and the reaction mixture cooled to 0°. To this was added dropwise with stirring benzyl chloroformate (1 ml) in methylene chloride (10 ml), under nitrogen atmosphere. The reaction mixture was further stirred overnight at room temperature, diluted with methylene chloride (200 ml), washed with water (3 × 50 ml), sodium bicarbonate solution (2 × 50 ml), brine (2 × 30 ml), dried (Na_2SO_4) and filtered. The filtrate on evaporation gave 25 (325 mg, 82%), m.p. 114-115° (ethyl acetate-petroleum ether) (Found: C, 65.93; H, 6.19; N, 3.50. Calcd. for $C_{22}H_{28}NO_6$: C, 66.15; H, 6.31; N, 3.51%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 450, 1 740, 1 510 and 830 cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 1.40 (3H, s), 1.64 (3H, s), 3.43 (1H, d, J 5.7 Hz), 3.77 (3H, s), 4.39 (1H, m), 4.73 (1H, dd, J 5.7 and 12.2 Hz), 4.98 (1H, dd, J 5 and 12.2 Hz), 5.16 (2H, s), 6.84 (2H, d, J 9 Hz) and 7.37 (7H, m); CIMS (reagent gas: NH_3) 417 (M+NH₄)⁺.

N-Unsubstituted bicyclic β-lactam (27): A solution of β-lactam 22d (522 mg, 0.002 mol) in acetonitrile (15 ml) was cooled to 0° in an ice-bath. To this cold mixture, a solution of ceric ammonium nitrate (3.28 g, 0.006 mol) in water (20 ml) was added over a period of 10 min. The reaction mixture was stirred further at -5 to 0° for 30 min. The progress of the reaction was monitored by tlc. It was then diluted with water (100 ml) and extracted with ethyl acetate (3 × 50 ml). The ethyl acetate extracts were washed with saturated $NaHCO_3$ solution (2 × 40 ml). The aqueous extracts were back-washed with ethyl acetate (50 ml). The combined ethyl acetate extracts were washed with sodium sulphite (until the aqueous layer remained colorless), brine, dried ($MgSO_4$) and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated to give crude 27 (300 mg). It was purified by silica gel (100-200 mesh) column chromatography using ethyl acetate-petroleum ether (6:4) as an eluent when pure 27 was obtained (150 mg, 48%), m.p. 99-101° (Found: C, 53.98; H, 5.67; N, 8.19. Calcd. for $C_7H_9NO_3$: C, 54.19; H, 5.85; N, 8.18%); ν_{\max} (nujol) 3 300, 1 770 and 1 740 cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 1.45 (3H, s), 1.63 (3H, s), 3.71 (1H, d, J 6 Hz), 4.31 (1H, d, J 6 Hz) and 6.66 (1H, bs); CIMS (reagent gas: NH_3) 173 (M+NH₄)⁺.

trans-1-p-Anisyl-3-(1'-hydroxyethyl)-4-carbethoxyazetidone-2-one (30): To the solution of β-lactam 18b (1.595 g, 0.005 mol) in DMF (15 ml), sodium chloride (585 mg, 0.01 mol) and water (0.18 ml, 0.01 mol) were added and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 8 h. DMF was removed under high vacuum. The residue was dissolved in methylene chloride (60 ml), and the solution was washed successively with water (3 × 20 ml), brine (2 × 20 ml) and dried (Na_2SO_4). It was then filtered and the filtrate on removal of solvent gave a crude oily product (1.2 g), which was purified by column chromatography (silica gel, 230-400 mesh, chloroform-ethyl acetate-petroleum ether 10.05:0.5) to give pure 30, (1.025 g, 70%) m.p. 48° (Found: C, 61.03; H, 6.46; N, 4.60. Calcd. for $C_{14}H_{19}NO_5$: C, 61.42; H, 6.53; N, 4.78%); ν_{\max} (nujol) 3 440 and 1 720 cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 1.25 (2H, t, J 7 Hz) 1.42 (3H, d, J 6 Hz), 3.36 (1H, dd, J 2.5 and 5.25 Hz), 3.77 (3H, s), 4.25 (3H, m), 4.39 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz), 6.84 (2H, d, J 9 Hz) and 7.25 (2H, d, J 9 Hz); CIMS (reagent gas: NH_3) 294 (M+H)⁺ and 311 (M+NH₄)⁺.

β-Lactam carbonate (31): A solution of β-lactam 30 (1.465 g, 0.005 mol), 4-dimethylaminopyridine (1.22 g, 0.01 mol) in methylene chloride (15 ml) was cooled to 0° and a solution of benzyl chloroformate (1.023 g, 0.006 mol) in methylene chloride (5 ml) was added slowly over a period of 15 min under N_2 atmosphere. The reaction mixture was stirred for 1 h at 0° followed by overnight stirring at room temperature. The reaction mixture was then diluted with methylene chloride and washed successively with dilute HCl (1N, 2 × 20 ml), water (3 × 20 ml), brine (2 × 20 ml) and dried (Na_2SO_4).

It was filtered and the filtrate on concentration gave a crude oil (2.125 g) which on purification by column chromatography (silica gel, 230-400 mesh; chloroform-ethyl acetate-petroleum ether, 10 : 0.5 : 0.5) gave **31** (1.92 g, 90%), m.p. 82-83° (Found : C, 65.08; H, 5.96; N, 3.36. Calcd. for $C_{23}H_{25}NO_7$: C, 64.63; H, 5.90; N, 3.28%); ν_{max} 1760, 1740 and 1725 cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 1.17 (3H, t, J 7 Hz), 1.45 (3H, d, J 7 Hz), 3.57 (1H, dd, J 2.5 and 5.5 Hz), 3.7 (3H, s), 4.18 (2H, q, J 7 Hz), 4.28 (2H, d, J 2.5 Hz), 5.1 (2H, s), 5.15 (1H, m), 6.80 (2H, d, J 9 Hz), 7.25 (2H, d, J 9 Hz) and 7.32 (5H, s); CIMS (reagent gas : NH_3) 428 ($M+H$)⁺ and 445 ($M+NH_4$)⁺.

p-Nitrobenzyl carbonate (**32**) : It was obtained in 85% yield from hydroxy β -lactam **30**, (2.344 g, 0.008 mol), DMAP (1.952 g, 0.016 mol), *p*-nitrobenzyl chloroformate (1.939 g, 0.009 mol) and methylene chloride (25 ml) by following a similar procedure as for compound **31**. m.p. 84-52° (Found : C, 58.60; H, 5.05; N, 5.86. Calcd. for $C_{23}H_{25}N_3O_8$: C, 58.47; H, 5.12; N, 5.93%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1720, 1705, 1705 and 1460 cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 1.25 (3H, t, J 7 Hz), 1.54 (2H, d, J 6.4 Hz), 3.61 (1H, dd, J 2.6 and 4.6 Hz), 3.78 (3H, s), 4.25 (2H, q, J 7 Hz), 4.32 (1H, d, J 2 Hz), 5.24 (2H, s), 5.3 (1H, m), 6.86 (2H, d, J 9 Hz), 7.24 (2H, d, J 9 Hz), 7.51 (2H, d, J 8.6 Hz) and 8.19 (2H, d, J 8.6 Hz).

N-Unsubstituted β -lactam (**33**) : It was prepared in 70% yield by the ceric ammonium nitrate oxidation of **31** by a similar method as described under the preparation of **27**, m.p. 89-90° (Found : C, 60.16, H, 5.71; N, 4.67. Calcd. for $C_{16}H_{19}NO_6$: C, 59.81; H, 5.96; N, 4.36%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1745, 1740 and 1725 cm^{-1} ; δ 1.25 (3H, t, 7 Hz), 1.45 (3H, d, J Hz), 3.65 (1H, dd, J 2.5 and 5 Hz), 4.5 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz), 4.21 (2H, q, J 7 Hz), 5.2 (3H, m), 6.35 (1H, s) and 7.45 (5H, s); CIMS (reagent gas : NH_3) 322 ($M+H$)⁺ and 339 ($M+NH_4$)⁺.

N-Unsubstituted β -lactam (**34**) : It was similarly prepared by CAN oxidation of **32** in 90% yield as white crystalline solid, m.p. 93-94° (Found : C, 52.32; H, 4.76; N, 7.63. Calcd. for $C_{16}H_{18}N_2O_6$: C, 52.46; H, 4.95; N, 7.65%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3230, 1750, 1730 and 1510 cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 1.29 (3H, t, J 7 Hz), 1.51 (3H, d, J 6 Hz), 3.55 (1H, dd, J 2.8 and 4.5 Hz), 4.05 (1H, d, J 2.8 Hz), 4.24 (2H, q, J 7 Hz), 5.16 (1H, m), 5.27 (2H, s), 6.22 (1H, b), 7.56 (2H, d, J 8.6 Hz) and 8.24 (2H, d, J 8.6 Hz); CIMS (reagent gas : NH_3) 384 ($M+NH_4$)⁺.

Reduction of β -lactam (**33**) : To a solution of β -lactam **33** (640 mg, 0.002 mol) in THF-water (4 : 1) (5 ml) cooled in ice-water was added a solution of sodium borohydride (740 mg, 0.02 mol) in THF-water (4 : 1) (5 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 12 h. THF was removed under vacuum and the residue was dissolved in methylene chloride (50 ml), washed with water (3 \times 20 ml), brine (2 \times 20 ml) and dried (Na_2SO_4). It was then filtered and the

filtrate after concentration gave crude **35** (500 mg). It was purified by column chromatography (silica gel, 230-240 mesh; chloroform-ethyl acetate-petroleum ether, 10 : 1 : 1) to **29** (400 mg, 82%), m.p. 87-88° (Found : C, 60.80; H, 6.29; N, 5.01. Calcd. for $C_{13}H_{17}NO_5$: C, 60.21; H, 6.14; N, 5.02%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3360 and 1740 cm^{-1} ; δ 1.38 (3H, d, J 7 Hz), 3.23 (1H, dd, J 2.5 Hz), 3.55-3.75 (4H, m), 5.05 (1H, m), 5.13 (2H, s), 6.81 (1H, s) and 7.32-7.38 (5H, m); CIMS (reagent gas : NH_3) 297 ($M+NH_4$)⁺.

Acylation of **30** : To an ice-cold solution of the hydroxy β -lactam **30** (146 mg, 5 mmol) and triethylamine (0.5 ml) in methylene chloride (10 ml) was added dropwise with constant stirring a solution of *p*-nitrobenzoyl chloride (110 mg, 6 mmol) in methylene chloride (5 ml) under anhydrous condition. After the addition, the reactants were brought to room temperature and stirred overnight. The reaction mixture was diluted with methylene chloride (100 ml), washed successively with water (2 \times 20 ml), saturated sodium bicarbonate solution (2 \times 20 ml), brine (2 \times 20 ml), dried (Na_2SO_4), filtered and evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure to afford the *p*-nitrobenzenzoate (**38**) (160 mg, 75%), m.p. 115-116°; ν_{max} (KBr) 1750, 1730, 1510 and 840 cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 1.23 (3H, t, J 7 Hz), 1.62 (3H, d, J 6.4 Hz), 3.72 (1H, dd, J 2.5 and 4.3 Hz), 3.79 (3H, s), 4.25 (2H, q, J 7 Hz), 4.36 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz), 5.65 (1H, m), 6.87 (2H, d, J 9 Hz), 7.27 (2H, d, J 9 Hz), 8.13 (2H, d, J 9 Hz), and 8.23 (2H, d, J 9 Hz); CIMS (reagent gas : NH_3) 443 ($M+H$)⁺ and 460 ($M+NH_4$)⁺.

Inversion at $C_{\alpha'}$ of the hydroxy β -lactam (**30**) : A solution of β -lactam **30** (293 mg, 0.001 mol), triphenyl phosphine (395 mg, 0.0015 mol) and *p*-nitrobenzoic acid (200 mg, 0.0012 mol) in dry THF (20 ml) was stirred at 0°. To this solution, was added dropwise a solution of diethyl azodicarboxylate (350 mg, 0.002 mol) in dry THF (5 ml), under N_2 atmosphere. The reactants were stirred overnight at room temperature and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The residue was purified by column chromatography (silica gel, 230-400 mesh; chloroform-petroleum ether-ethyl acetate, 10 : 1 : 0.5) to give pure **37** (390 mg, 85%) m.p. 114-115° (Found : C, 57.61; H, 5.03; N, 6.34. Calcd. for $C_{23}H_{25}N_2O_6$: C, 57.64; H, 4.84; N, 6.11%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1750, 1725 and 1510 cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 1.18 (3H, t, J 7 Hz), 1.61 (3H, d, J 6 Hz), 3.61 (1H, dd, J 2.3 and 7.2 Hz), 3.79 (3H, s), 4.23 (2H, q, J 7 Hz), 4.57 (1H, d, J 2.3 Hz), 5.61 (1H, m), 6.87 (2H, d, J 9 Hz), 7.27 (2H, d, J 9 Hz), 8.13 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz) and 8.24 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz); CIMS reagent gas : NH_3) 459 ($M+H$)⁺.

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